

STAGES OF FORMATION OF TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In the article the author has classified and shown the stages of the formation of tourism infrastructure in Uzbekistan.

Key words: tourism, infrastructure, economy, service, tourist, currency, income, transport, hotel, organizational and economic, "Uzbektourism" NK.

Annotasiya: Maqolada muallif O'zbekistonda turizm infratuzilmasining shakllanishi bosqichlarini davrlashtirgan va ko'rsatib bergan.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm, infratuzilma, iqtisodiyot, xizmat, sayyoh, valyuta, daromad, transport, mehmonxona, tashkiliy-iqtisodiy, "O'zbekturizm" MK.

Аннотация: В статье автор описывает и иллюстрирует этапы становления туристической инфраструктуры в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: туризм, инфраструктура, экономика, услуга, турист, валюта, доход, транспорт, гостиница, организационно-экономический, НК «Узбектуризм».

Introduction. As a result of the Republic of Uzbekistan gaining its independence on September 1, 1991, economic reforms began to be carried out in the country at an accelerated pace. Similarly, the national tourism infrastructure began to take shape in these years. The formation and development of the national tourism infrastructure began to be led by the National Company "Uzbektourism". At that time, in the development of tourism in our republic, the National Company "Uzbektourism" was considered an economic organization with the rights to conduct state administration and foreign economic activity.

It would not be wrong to say that the formation and development of the national tourism infrastructure began in these years. Reforms began to be implemented gradually in order to form and develop national tourism.

Analysis and results. The first stage of economic reforms and infrastructure reconstruction in the national tourism system can be said to have begun in 1992. This reform, which began in the republic, was carried out on the basis of a new economy (market economy). During this period, organizational, economic and management processes were formed. The "Uzbektourism" State

Enterprise was founded and the directions of tourism development were identified.

The second stage of economic reform of the tourism industry covers 1993-1995. During this period, a national model for the development of tourism infrastructure was developed. This stage showed that, along with the growth of tourist services, a number of problems needed to be solved. These problems were related to the development of new tourist routes, improving service provision, expanding the material and technical base of tourism, further improving management and creating a legal framework, and it became clear that they could not be solved only within the framework of the "Uzbektourism" State Enterprise.

In the process of infrastructure restructuring, a number of tourist facilities were removed from the state network and privatized. Significant changes were made in the hotel industry (new hotels were built, the number of rooms increased).

Thus, by the end of 1993, 123 organizations with legal and independent balance sheets were operating in the tourism system of our republic.

From July 1, 1995, the third stage of development began to be implemented. At the same time, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs established a single tourist visa valid throughout the country (except for facilities designated by the state). Another bright step in the development of tourism was the approval by the Cabinet of Ministers of the national program "Heritage", aimed at the preservation and reproduction of historical and cultural monuments, architectural structures, and created works of art. During this period, regulations were developed on special open economic zones for international tourism in Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva. In order to establish direct contacts with tour operators, the Uzbek Tourism Company opened its representative offices (representatives) in countries where Uzbekistan has air connections. In Germany (Frankfurt), Great Britain (London), the USA (New York), the United Arab Emirates (Sharjah), and Russia (Moscow).

In 1996-1997, the fourth stage of improving and reforming the tourism infrastructure was carried out. At the same time, active privatization began in the service sector. In 1996, 90% of the total number of tourist facilities in the Uzbek Tourism Company system was de-stated. A new type of development has entered Uzbek tourism since that time.

Since 1998, Uzbekistan has entered the fifth stage of tourism reform. This is a stage of recovery, and a number of reforms have been implemented to ensure

the balanced development of infrastructure. As a result, this has led to an increase in export potential, a stable flow of foreign exchange, tourists, private capital and investment. By the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers "On improving the organization of tourism organizations", the State Corporation "Uzbektourism" was reorganized and its organizational and managerial structure, powers and functions were expanded. At the same time, the Association of Private Tourism Organizations of Uzbekistan was founded.

Since May 1999, the sixth stage of tourism reform has begun. At the same time, the adopted decree "On the Development of Tourism" created the basis for firmly defining the position of national and international tourism in the country, its economic foundations. This document created additional customs privileges for tourism organizations. In addition, the position of tourism advisor for diplomatic representatives of Uzbekistan abroad was introduced. In August 1999, the Oliy Majlis adopted the Law "On Tourism" and created a legal framework for the functioning of this sector of the economy.

At this time, the tourism infrastructure in Uzbekistan was relatively well-formed and, at its sixth stage, set itself a number of important tasks:

- A. Further development of tourism companies and improvement of management in them;
- B. Integration into the international tourism system as a highly developed industry;
- C. Constant improvement of the strategy and tactics of reforms in the tourism sector of the economy;
- D. Directing the necessary funds and investments to the reserves of the republic's tourism potential to build a tourism infrastructure that meets "World Standards";
- E. Increasing the capacity of tourist facilities to receive tourists, which is one of the factors seriously limiting the flow of tourists;
- F. With the transition of the economy to market relations, new requirements are put forward for the quality and nomenclature of services, various forms and methods of providing tourism and excursion services;
- G. Attracting direct foreign investment for the purpose of establishing tourist joint ventures, joint production and construction of tourist complexes, and renovation of existing facilities;
- H. Increasingly organizing joint ventures in the republic in which entrepreneurs from America, Turkey, Pakistan, Germany, India, Italy and other countries will operate as equal partners;

I. Among the preferential areas for foreign investment, the tasks of creating a modern tourism infrastructure, including transport, telecommunications, information services, and creating broad opportunities for entrepreneurial activity were set.

It was noted that without implementing these tasks, it is practically impossible to transition to real market relations and develop international investment activities widely. Despite this, the tasks set were not sufficiently fulfilled, and it became clear that there are still some problems in fully forming the infrastructure. For example, for many years, income from tourism did not exceed 1.5% of GDP, while in other countries this figure is 10-40% of GDP. The main part of the tourist flow fell on the main tourist centers of our country - Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva. However, insufficient attention was paid to the systematic development of the infrastructure of a number of promising regions of our country.

Conditions for the development of such types of tourism as educational, scientific, religious, pilgrimage, ecological, sports and recreation have not been created. The need to seriously improve the quality of services provided, the use of modern effective forms and methods of attracting tourists, and the introduction of modern information and communication technologies into the national tourism industry has been ignored.

The organization and development of domestic tourism, including youth tourism, has not been properly established. The ideological and content enrichment of tourist destination programs for students of schools, colleges and lyceums, the preparation of comprehensively developed materials explaining the history and significance of cultural heritage sites have not been carried out to a sufficient extent.

Many tourist organizations and their employees have not received sufficient training to provide the necessary information about tourist sites that are monuments of the unique spiritual wealth and historical heritage of the people of Uzbekistan. In this regard, the training, retraining and advanced training programs for personnel in the tourism sector, guides, tour guides, and employees of tourist and hotel organizations have not been significantly improved.

It has become necessary to quickly resolve these problems and reshape the tourism infrastructure in line with international requirements..

Conclusion. By 2016, the State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan was unable to fully fulfill its mission. In order to

eliminate such accumulated problems, a new seventh stage of reforms in tourism was introduced. Today's integration processes and the demands of tourists required a new approach to meeting them and organizing tourism infrastructure.

Taking this into account, on December 2, 2016, the President adopted the Decree No. PF-4861 "On measures to ensure the accelerated development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan". According to the Decree, the State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established on the basis of the State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the committee was designated as an authorized state body in the field of tourism, and at the same time, it is an organization implementing all issues and actions related to the development of tourism.

Table 1

Stages of formation and development of tourism infrastructure in the Republic of Uzbekistan¹

Stages	Brief information about the scope of work carried out
First stage -	The organizational, economic and management processes of tourism were formed and the development directions were identified. The Uzbektourism State Enterprise was established.
1992	A national model for the development of tourism infrastructure was developed. In the process of reshaping the infrastructure, a number of tourist facilities were removed from the state network and privatized. Significant changes were made in the hotel industry (new hotels were built, the number of rooms increased).
Second stage - 1993-1995	The Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan established a single tourist visa valid throughout the country (except for facilities designated by the state). The "Heritage" national program was developed, aimed at the preservation and reproduction of historical and cultural monuments, architectural structures, and works of art. Regulations on special open economic zones for international tourism in Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva were developed. The Uzbektourism State Enterprise opened its representative offices (representatives) in countries with which Uzbekistan

	has air connections. In Germany (Frankfurt), Great Britain (London), USA (New York), United Arab Emirates (Sharjah), Russia (Moscow).
Third stage - 1995	90% of the total number of tourist facilities in the system of the "Uzbektourism" MC was de-stated. A new type of development has entered the tourism of our republic.
Fourth stage - 1996-1997	There was a stage of recovery, and a number of reforms were implemented to ensure the balanced development of infrastructure. Export potential was increased, a stable flow of foreign exchange, tourists, private capital and investment was ensured. The "Uzbektourism" MC was reorganized. The Association of Private Tourist Organizations of Uzbekistan was founded.
Fifth stage - 1998	Additional customs privileges were created for tourist organizations. The position of tourism advisor was introduced among diplomatic representatives of Uzbekistan abroad. The Law "On Tourism" was adopted
	Measures were developed for the rapid development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established on the basis of the Uzbektourism State Committee. Free tourist zones (FTZs) were established. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Tourism", updated and revised to regulate tourist activities, was adopted.

The Tourism Committee is mainly engaged in a number of issues, such as developing all types of tourism in the republic, creating its material and technical base and infrastructure, raising the level of service to tourists to world standards, increasing foreign exchange earnings for our economy, disseminating information about the historical and cultural monuments of the republic to the world (conducting propaganda and agitation work), training personnel for the tourism sector, and creating new jobs.

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